

EDUCATIONAL REFORMS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN AS AN EXAMPLE OF PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS. NEW EDUCATIONAL METHODS IN PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS

Sunnatillo Ismailov

Teacher of the Presidential School in Tashkent

Abstract: The future of the country is directly related to the level of education of the youth. Therefore, it is an important task of every country to pay attention to the development of the education system at the government level. In recent years, within the framework of the Strategy of Actions and its logical continuation, the Strategy of Development, significant reforms have been implemented in Uzbekistan to regularly improve the continuous education system, provide quality education, and train qualified personnel, as in developed countries.

Key words: Educational reforms, Presidential schools, method, technology.

Developing the intellectual and creative potential of young people, creating the necessary conditions for supporting and encouraging talented children, raising the level of their legal consciousness and legal culture is one of the most important directions of the state policy in the field of public education. The rapid development of the country in the future requires the need to improve the quality of work on identifying young talents, organizing the system of selecting and training talented children, and creating a multidisciplinary educational environment that helps to manifest the intellectual potential of the growing generation. is doing. Identifying gifted children, creating a comprehensive system for their education and upbringing using advanced technologies in the educational process, further support and encouragement of talented young people, mature and intellectual in accordance with the State Program on the formation of a competent generation, as well as the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Active

Investments and Social Development", 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan In accordance with the Decision No. PQ-4199 of February 20, Presidential schools in the form of specialized state general education institutions were established in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent. Today, 24 teachers and 168 students organize the activities of the Presidential School in Tashkent, and today this educational institution is achieving several achievements.

In particular, you can learn about the results and research of Malika Tokhirova, a teacher of mathematics at the Presidential School in Tashkent, below.

- Two-time winner of the Republican stage of the student science Olympiad "Mathematics and its teaching methodology" held in 2018-2019;

- In 2021, "Public Education a was awarded with the "lochisi" badge;

- IELTS in 2020, CEFR (B2) certificates in 2022;

- Successfully completed "Introductory AS&A level (9709)" and "Professional Development Qualification" training courses organized by Cambridge International Education in 2021;

- He is an international teacher of the A-level exam, and his students have the highest A-level certificates;

- Author of the methodical guide "Mathematical example and problem solving methodology";

- Doctoral student of TDPU named after Nizomi: in scientific research on the topic "Strategies for the development of intellectual potential of students based on international experiences"; His articles on topics such as "General concept of mathematics teaching technology", "Methodology and subject of teaching mathematics", "The role of information and communication technologies in quality teaching of mathematics" were published in international magazines and conferences. His students have been accepted into the national team of the Republic and have been winning at the International Olympiads. Including:

- Bronze medal at the International Junior Science Olympiad (IJSO);

☐ Silver and bronze medals at the Caucasus International Mathematics Olympiad;

- ☐ 1st place in the Republic Mathematics Olympiad;
- ☐ They got 16 A* and 18 A grades in A-level exams.

Husnullin Shamil, a student of the Presidential School in Tashkent, won the gold medal at the CIMOC-2023 (Singapore International Math Olympiad Challenge) Olympiad. For reference, the Singapore International Math Olympiad Challenge (SIMOC) is a prestigious annual competition for young math enthusiasts from around the world.

Sohibjon Dilmurodov, a student of the President's School in Tashkent, scored 8.5 points in the IELTS exam. For information, Sahibjon Dilmurodov

- ☐ SAT 1520 points
- ☐ "International Olympiad of natural sciences among teenagers - ISJO-2021" - bronze medal;
- ☐ International Mendeleev Chemistry Olympiad - silver medal;
- ☐ Beruni Olympiad - silver medal;
- ☐ International Chemistry Olympiad -2023 - bronze medal;
- ☐ MathLeague - silver medal;
- ☐ AMO - bronze medal;
- ☐ "Zakovat" student league 2022-2023 season absolute winner - a member of the "Et Cetera" team;
- ☐ ClimateScience - bronze medal;
- ☐ Chemistry Olympiad in Tashkent - 2nd place;
- ☐ Agency Olympiad - 1st place winner.

Abdukhakimov Abdusalih, a student of the Presidential School in Tashkent, scored 1450 points in the SAT exam. For information, Abdusalih Abduhakimov

- ✓ ☐ IELTS 7.5 points

✓ SIMOC (Singapore International Math Olympiad Challenge) Olympiad
- bronze medal;

✓ SASMO (Singapore & Asian schools Math Olympiad) Olympiad -
bronze medal;

✓ VANDA Olympiad - silver medal;

✓ "ClimateScience

"Olympiad 2023" is a quarter finalist.

Academic Director of the Presidential School in Tashkent, Miss Anmarie Anderson, "Excellence of Public Education" badge; Chemistry teacher Ilyas Khudoinazarov "Fame" medal; ➡ Russian language teacher Nigora Muksinova was awarded with the "Excellence of Public Education" badge.

Abdujalilov Saidaziz, a student of the 11th "Green" grade of the President's school in Tashkent, and G'ulomov Pakhlavon, a student of the 9th "Blue" grade, won the finals of the "Zayed Sustainability Prize" with their modern water purification project. entered It should be noted that the projects of school students who are winners of this award are financed with 100 thousand US dollars annually. Over the past 15 years, the award has funded 106 projects that have positively impacted the lives of more than 378 million people worldwide. The winners will be announced at an award ceremony on December 1 within the framework of the 28th Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change - COP28 UAE, which will be held from November 30 to December 12. Finalists, including students from our school, are invited to participate in this conference, and all expenses are covered by the Zayed Sustainability Prize.

Abdukakhhorova Farangiz, a 9th-grade student of the Presidential School in Tashkent, scored 7.5 points in the IELTS exam. For information, Farangiz Abdukahhorova is a semi-finalist of the

"Technovation Girls" international competition;

□ "StemCo-2023" - winner of the silver medal at the Olympiad; Bronze medalist at the "PIMSO" Olympiad.

Students of the Presidential School in Tashkent:

□ Boxirbek Ibrohimov and Abdulhamid Khidirov won the 1st place in the international Olympiad "STEM Olympiad - innovations in education" held in Astana, Kazakhstan;

Saidaziz Abdusalilov and Pakhlavon Gulomov were recognized as authors of one of the best 3 projects selected from European and Central Asian countries at the "Zayed Sustainability Award COP28"; We reported that Javahir Mamadaliyev won a silver medal at the 20th International Youth Olympiad in Natural Sciences held in Thailand.

"There is no doubt that the reforms implemented in the education system will serve as a foundation for the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. We are very happy with the achievements of our children in response to the opportunities created.

Several modern methods are used in the presidential school. The word method is a Greek word that means research, a way to achieve a goal, a method. A method - in the most general sense - is a method of achieving a goal, an activity organized in a certain way. The main content of the methods is scientific theories tested in practice. Any scientific theory essentially has a methodological function. The method, in turn, becomes a tool for the discovery of new scientific theories and laws. Educational methods mean the totality of teaching methods of the teacher and the organization of students' learning activities in order to solve various didactic tasks aimed at mastering the studied material. Educational methods first appear in the pedagogue's mind in the form of a general project of activity in a certain direction. This project is put into practice as a set of specific actions, actions or methods aimed at the interaction of teacher and student activities, teaching and learning. The method does not appear in other forms, because of this, the educational method represents the didactic model of activity in

general. In didactics, the term educational methods is also widely used. The educational method means the joint activities of the teacher and students aimed at achieving the expected goal in the educational process. Teaching methods determine the activity of the teacher and student in the educational process, how to organize and conduct the teaching process. Educational method - a component or separate aspect of the educational method. Methods and method relations are interconnected. Method and method are connected to each other as a whole and a part. Only a part of the pedagogical or educational task is solved with the help of methods. Some teachers use the concept of "style" instead of the concept of "method". But the concept of "style" cannot fully reflect the essence of the term "method". Because the method has a more specific (in this case, it expresses the specificity of the teacher) description and cannot serve as a way to achieve a specific goal. Didactic studies show that the nomenclature (naming) and classification of educational methods are very different depending on the chosen approach to their development. We will focus on the most important of them. Therefore, educational methods are classified as follows:

1. Traditional educational methods: oral, visual, practical, working with books and video methods.

2. Educational methods according to the description of students' cognitive activity: Information-receptive, reproductive, problem statement, heuristic (partial search), research.

3. Educational methods according to the main didactic goals:

- a) acquisition of new knowledge;
- b) formation of skills and qualifications; d) applying knowledge in practice.

4. Educational methods according to the holistic approach:

- a) methods of strengthening and controlling knowledge, skills and abilities;
- b) methods of organizing and implementing educational activities;
- d) methods of motivating and encouraging educational activities;
- c) methods of control and self-control of educational activities.

5. Interactive methods and graphic organizers.

a) methods of encouraging students to learn;

b) methods of understanding new material;

d) methods that allow thinking about what has been learned.

Demonstration methods are also of special importance in ensuring the quality and efficiency of education. Although the image (illustration) method is closely related to the demonstration method, it is studied separately in didactics. Illustration requires the representation of things, events and processes with the help of their symbolic representations - drawings, pictures, photographs, flat models, etc. The demonstration method is useful in revealing the dynamics of the studied object, and at the same time, it is widely used to provide complete information about the external appearance and internal structure of the object. When presenting natural objects, attention is usually paid to its external appearance (shape, size, quantity, color, parts, their mutual relations), and then to the study of its internal structure or special features. Demonstration is often observed using a subject or a drawing of the object being studied. Practical method - requires the application of acquired knowledge in a process aimed at finding solutions to practical problems. In this, the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice is formed. Practical work is carried out in the classroom or in natural conditions - school grounds, greenhouses, geographical areas. The actions taken during their implementation are controlled by the teacher and, in necessary cases, the instruction or special instruction is brought to the attention of the students.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh M “Bilimli avlod – buyuk kelajakning, tadbirkor xalq – farovon hayotning, do’stona hamkorlik esa taraqqiyotning kafolatidir” mavzusidagi O’zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi qabul qilinganining 26 yilligiga bag’ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi ma’ruzasi “Xalq so’zi” gazetasi 2018-yil 8-dekabr

2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 16 fevraldagi "Oliy o'quv yurtidan keyingi ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish to'g'risida" gi PF-4958 sonli Farmoni.

3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Ta'lim- tarbiya tizimini yanada takomillashtirishga oid qo'shimcha chora- tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi qarori 2020-yil 6 noyabr

4. Xaliqulova H O'zbekistonda inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish borasida xalqaro hamkorlik. 2020.